

Planning and Development of Education in Nigeria: the Role Of African Union (Au)

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ABSTRACT

Education is the most important means through which a nation such as Nigeria or a continent like Africa has to develop human resources, impart relevant skills for self, national and continental development as well as transmit required knowledge and positive attitudes to her citizens. The educational system of any nation such as Nigeria is too complex that the planning and development of the system cannot be left in the hand of the government alone. This paper examined the planning and development of education in Nigeria with particular reference to the role of African Union (AU). This paper also discussed the African Union (AU) and its objectives, African Union (AU) policy on education in Nigeria, the agency through which the African Union (AU) executes its policy on education in Nigeria, the source of funding the African Union (AU) policy on education, African Union's (AU) role in planning and development of education in Nigeria, challenges of African Union (AU) on development of education, achievements of African Union (AU) in the planning and development of education in Nigeria and the way forward. The paper concluded that Nigeria as member state of AU should always avoid any form of delay in implementing the action plans on education by AU and should regularly give her maximum consent and support to the plans.

Key Words: Planning; Development; Education; African Union

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is acknowledged as the vehicle for sustainable development of many nations in any continent, such as Africa. Education as a critical sector directly affects and determines the quality and magnitude of many nations' development in any continent. No nation or continent can attain meaningful development devoid of effective planning of her educational system in general (Mbaji & Ebirim, 2015; Ebirim, 2023). Education forms the foundation for developing innovations; science and technology to harness resources, industrialize and participate in the global knowledge economy. For a continent to take its rightful place in the global community, such continent must plan and develop the standard of educational levels of many nations in the continent. The African Union as an organization within the African continent needs to ensure that the education of any nation in Africa, such as Nigeria, is effectively planned and sustained to ensure lasting development of the continent. Nigeria needs to plan and develop its educational system adequately with the support of the African Union as an organization within the continent of Africa. In planning and development of education in Nigeria, many factors have to come into play. The government and other agencies outside the government have to

play some roles to ensure effective planning and development of education in Nigeria. This paper therefore looks at the role of African Union (AU) in the planning and development of education in Nigeria, considering the challenges and prospects.

1.1 AFRICAN UNION (AU) AND ITS OBJECTIVES

The African Union (AU) is the successor organization to the Organization of African Unity (OAU). Currently, the African Union (AU) is a union of 55 member states which represent countries on the African Continent. The member states are grouped geographic regions namely; the Central Africa; Eastern Africa; Northern Africa; Southern Africa; and Western Africa (African Union Webmail, 2024). The AU was founded on 9 July in 2002 as a successor of the Organization of African Unity to promote unity and solidarity of African states, to spur economic development and to promote international cooperation (Britannica, 2014). The commission is the secretariat of the union entrusted with executive functions. The AU headquarters secretariat is located at Addis Ababa in Ethiopia. The African Union (AU) Commission's secretariat consists of 10 officials; headed by a Chairperson, a Deputy Chairperson, Eight (8) Commissioners and Staff Members (African Union Commission, 2024). The structure represents the union and protects its interest under the auspices of the Assembly of Heads of State and Government as well as the Executive Committee (Prevention Web, 2024). The main task of the African Union Commission (AUC) is to implement the decisions of the AU organs.

The AU Commission is made up of portfolios that involve peace and security; political affairs; trade and industry; infrastructure and energy; social affairs; rural economy and agriculture; human resources; science and technology; and economic affairs. The most important decisions of the AU are made by the Assembly of Heads of States and Government. These involve the meeting of all the Heads of State and Governments of its member states (African Union.org). The Assembly determines the AU's policies, establishes its policies, adopts its annual programme and monitors the implementation of its policies and decisions. The initiatives, institutions and programmes of the AU and its flagship economic and education development programme depend on the effort of its sub-regional organizations. Africa's sub-regional organizations consist Southern Africa Development Community (SADC), Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA); Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the Arab Maghreb Union (AMU), Intergovernmental Authority for Development (IGAD) (www.afdb.org; www.usaid.gov). The primary goal of the African Union is to drive the "integration and development process" with union members, regional communities and African citizens. The organization is an educational and information source that places "Africa above all else" (ask.com). The objectives of the African Union as contained in the Constitutive Act derived from Wikipedia (2014) are to:

Achieve greater unity and solidarity among African countries and the people of Africa; Defend the sovereignty, territorial integrity and independence

of its Member States; Accelerate the political and socio-economic integration of the continent; Promote and defend African common positions on issues of interest to the continent and its peoples; Encourage international cooperation, taking due account of the Charter of the United Nations and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights; Promote peace, security and stability in the continent; Promote democratic principles and institutions, popular participation and good governance; Promote and protect human peoples' rights in accordance with the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights and other relevant human rights instruments; Establish the necessary conditions which enable the continent to play its rightful role in the global economy and in international negotiations; Promote sustainable development at the economic, social and cultural levels as well as the integration of African economies; Promote cooperation in all fields of human activity to raise the living standards of African people; Coordinate and harmonize the policies between the existing and future Regional Economic Communities for the gradual attainment of the objectives of the Union; Advance the development of the continent by promoting research in all fields most importantly, in science and technology; and Work with relevant international partners in the eradication of preventable diseases and the promotion of good health on the continent.

The African Union, according to Paterson (2012), aims to promote the unity and solidarity of African states; to coordinate and intensify their cooperation and efforts to achieve a better life for the continent is over 800 million citizens; to defend their sovereignty, territorial integrity, and independence; to eradicate all forms of colonialism from Africa; to promote international cooperation, giving due regard to the Charter of the United Nations (1945) and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948); and to coordinate and harmonize member states' political, diplomatic, economic, educational, cultural, health, welfare, scientific, technical, and defence policies. Meanwhile, the current population of Africa is stated to be one billion, four hundred and eighty million, seven hundred and sixty one thousand, nine hundred and twenty eight (1,480,761,928) as of Saturday, February 3, 2024 based on the latest United Nations estimates (Worldometer, 2024). The continental body also seeks to boost development, eradicate poverty, and incorporate Africa into the global economy.

2. AFRICAN UNION (AU) POLICY ON EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

The African Union (AU) policy on education in Nigeria anchored on the First and Second Decades Plan of Action on Education for Africa (African Union, 2006). The First Decades of Education for Africa (1997-2006) focused on the activities of four priority areas, which include;

- Equity and access to basic education;
- Quality, relevance and effectiveness of education;
- Complementary learning modalities and;
- Capacity building.

The Second Decades of Education for Africa (2006-2015) (African Union, 2006:4) focused on the activities of seven priority areas. They are:-

Gender and culture; Education management information systems;
 Teacher development;
 Tertiary education;
 Technical and vocational education and training, including education in difficult situations;
 Curriculum, and teaching and learning materials;
 Quality management.

From the plan of action decade of education for Africa, the aim of African Union policy on education in Nigeria are:-

- To eliminate gender disparities and ensure gender equality, girls and women’s empowerment throughout the education system, while enriching the system with the positive aspects of African cultural values;
- To reverse the current phenomenon of ‘data blank’ and facilitate planning based on sound information; and rigorous monitoring and evaluation of the performance of education systems. The availability of well-functioning and sustainable EMIS, at continental, regional and national levels is a necessity for this function;
- To ensure the provision of sufficient teachers to meet the demands of education systems and to ensure that all teachers are properly qualified and possess the relevant knowledge, skills and attitudes to teach, effectively. Teachers should also be properly supported and adequately remunerated, to ensure high levels of motivation;
- To complete revitalization of higher education in Africa, with the emergence of strong and vibrant institutions profoundly engaged in fundamental and development-oriented research, teaching, community outreach and enrichment services to the lower levels of education; and functioning in an environment of academic freedom and institutional autonomy, within an overall framework of public accountability;
- To ensure that education systems in Member States are better able to provide the young generation with quality education that imparts key generic competences, skills and attitudes that lead to a culture of lifelong learning and entrepreneurship in order to fit them into an ever-changing world of work;
- To ensure the development and provision of balanced, relevant, responsive and culturally sensitive curricula adequately supported by appropriate teaching and learning materials, in all forms and levels of Education in Member States;
- To support improved access, relevance, equity and efficiency of Education in Africa through the development and sustenance of sound, quality management systems at national, regional and continental levels.

To enhance the chances of success, AU (2006:2) proposed that (African-Union.org) the following principles will guide the implementation of the Plan of Action of the Second Decade of Education:

- Ensuring enhanced political support particularly at national levels, but also at regional, continental and international levels;
- Concentration on strategic issues whose implementation will make a significant difference within Member States and also at the regional level;

Enhancing mutual assistance among African States;

Enhancing the capacities of Regional Economic Communities and national implementation mechanisms; Establishing strong and effective monitoring and oversight mechanisms at all levels; Avoiding the creation of new structures, by capitalizing on existing structures; Institutionalizing exchange of documentation, sharing and celebrating of positive experiences and promising initiatives among Member States; Institutionalizing collaboration and mutual support between countries and avoiding unnecessary duplication of initiatives.

It is believed that through the forgoing principles, the implementation of the Plan of Action will be successfully done.

2.2 THE AGENCY THROUGH WHICH THE AFRICAN UNION EXECUTES ITS POLICY ON EDUCATION

In collaboration with the African Union Commission (AUC) through various agencies and bodies of the continent, such as the Conference of Ministers of Education of the African Union (COMEDAF), Pan African Universities (PAU), Association of African Universities (AAU), Association for the Development of Education in Africa (ADEA), African Development Bank (ADB), Forum for African Women (FAWE), Africa Network Campaign on Education for All (ANCEFA), Regional Economic Communities (RECs) of the African Union and United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the AU discharges its policy on education plan (African Union, 2006; Paterson, 2012 and Africa Network Campaign on Education For All (ANCEFA, 2015). In Nigeria, the AU discharges her plan of action on education through the Ministry of Education (MOE); education regulatory bodies such as the Nigerian Universities Commission (NUC), National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), National Board for Technical Education (NBTE); Civil Societies, Financial Institutions and the Regional Economic Communities such as the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS).

2.3 SOURCES OF FUNDING AFRICAN UNION (AU) POLICY ON EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

African Union (AU) Policy on Education is usually funded internally from the resources of the Member States. According to the AU (2006:2), the action plan on education for Africa will be primarily self-funded from the internal resources of Member States. In Nigeria, AU education programmes are primarily funded by the Federal Government through the Ministry of Education and other education fund agencies such as Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF), Petroleum Technology Development Fund (PTDF) and Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) among others in the nation. It is expected that intra-continental support for the poorest countries by wealthier African countries will become institutionalized a regular practice. Finally, it is also expected that Regional Economic Communities (RECs) will pool countries' efforts to foster intra-regional collaboration, facilitate the implementation of the Plan of Action and monitor progress.

3. AFRICAN UNION'S (AU) ROLE IN PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION

Education is acknowledged by African Union (AU) as the major means by which Africa's citizens would be prepared for its crucial role in attaining integrated, peaceful and prosperous Africa driven by its people to take its rightful place in the global community and the knowledge economy. For this purpose, AU plays distinct role on education advocacy, monitoring, evaluation and implementation of education policy in Nigeria particularly, and Africa in general, through her continental, regional and national authorities as dictated by the nature of their specific mandates (African Union, 2006:4).

Through the African Union Commission, AU provides political oversight functions, advocacy at national and international levels. AU also ensures effective coordination of the regional economic communities, management of the continental education observatory, the organization of biannual review conferences, and the publication of continental overview reports on education.

AU also ensures effective coordination and monitoring of country-level activities, development of regional programmes and projects on education through the Regional Economic Communities such as ECOWAS, in Nigeria. AU assists in facilitation of regional consultative meetings on education, provision of country and regional reports to the AU Commission, and publications of region-specific reports on education.

Through the Member States National Authorities (governments through education ministries and agencies and civil society), AU involves in the direct implementation of the Decade programme, in the overall context of national education and development agenda, exchange of experiences and collaboration with countries within and outside the region, national-level monitoring and reporting to national and regional coordinating bodies.

4. CHALLENGES OF THE AFRICAN UNION (AU) IN PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

The African Union (AU) has faced many challenges in its efforts to attain the vision it has for Africa through planning and development of education in the continent. In the bid to achieve this vision, many challenges, such as delay in the implementation of the action plan, non-compliance to the plan of action on education, lack of support from Africa's development partners, poor funding as well as challenges in resourcing the plan of action on education have hindered their efforts in the planning and development of education.

The major challenge of AU in the development of education in Nigeria is the issue of delay

in the implementation and total compliance with the action plan. The AU Plan of Action on education was not immediately adopted after the formal launch of the decade (African Union, 2006). There was also little evidence of ownership by the government, their agencies, and other stakeholders, while publicity was grossly ineffective. Contrary to expectations, the AU plan of action on Education in Nigeria had little or no support from Nigeria's development partners, most of whom also developed their own Nigeria specific programmes, not linked with the AU plan of action on education, during the period.

At the national level, Member States negotiated their education sector development programmes with development partners, but this was not done within the overall context of achieving the goals of the Decade. There is also this issue of poor funding as the implementation of the AU plans on education anchored primarily on self-funding from the internal resources of member states of which Nigeria is one of the members and support from other bodies of the continent. There is another challenge of resourcing the AU policy on education in Nigeria. The challenges in resourcing the AU policy on education in Nigeria include; ensuring the availability of the appropriate quality in knowledge and skills; and availability of adequate numbers of human resources for implementing the Plan of Action. AU faces the challenge of inadequate supply of the appropriate numbers and quality of personnel-teachers, instructor, technician especially in hitherto deprived areas.

5. ACHIEVEMENTS OF AFRICAN UNION (AU) IN PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

Despite the challenges African Union (AU) faces in the planning and development of education in Nigeria particularly, and the Africa in general, some level of achievement has been recorded. AU has assisted in making some critical decisions and demands for urgent actions to accelerate program towards Education For All (EFA) and Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in Nigeria, These, include improving the quality and relevance of education in Nigeria by paying due attention to teachers' training and incentives; and vocational training for young Nigerians. AU has assisted in advocating for improved mobilization and utilization of financial resources in favour of the education sector in Nigeria. AU has encouraged the establishment of Education Development Fund in Nigeria. AU encouraged adapting of innovative sources such as domestic financing through taxation and contribution from industries (Education International, 2012).

AU advocated mutual assistance which lays strong emphasis on capacity building for human resources, encouragement of teachers' professional development programmes and the strengthening of education institutions in Nigeria. AU advocated for improved curriculum that contributes to positive knowledge, skills, attitudes, value and practices (Education International, 2012). AU advocated for the elimination of gender disparities and encouragement of gender equality, girls', women's and youth empowerment throughout the education system of Nigeria.

THE WAY FORWARD

1. The African Union should place economic sanction on any member state that delays in implementing the action plan on education with the equivalent period delayed. The economic sanction will motivate the member states in fast tracking the implementation of any action plan agreed upon education within the continent.
2. The African Union should always provide an effective communication means to create awareness for member states to see the plan as theirs and comply with the plan of action on education.
3. African Union should form an organ for coordinating all available Africa development partners. This is because, when a partner sees herself as part of the body to AU, the partner will be encouraged to support whatever good policy on education being provided.
4. African Union should have a joint account with all the member states. The chairperson of the AU commission should be the principal signatory to the account, while the Assemble of Heads of State should be the partners. They should also have a Central Bank of Africa and establish a unitary currency for Africa.
5. African Union should establish AU educational institutions in every member state specifically to minimize or even eradicate the challenges in resourcing the plan of action on education.

CONCLUSION

The role of African Union (AU) in planning and development of education in Nigeria cannot be taken for granted. AU provides advocacy on education, assists in monitoring, evaluation and implementation of education decades for Nigeria. As a member state of the African Union, Nigeria should always avoid any form of delay in implementing any action plan on education by African Union and give her maximum consent and support to the plans.

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